

A Queer Theory, Judith Butler's Theory of Gender as Performative In Jeanette Winterson's *Oranges Are Not The Only Fruit*

Ms.M.Sasiprabha, Assistant Professor of English, JP College of Arts and Science, Tenkasi.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5058576

ORCID: 0000-0001-9186-1807

Abstract

This paper attempts to examine aspects related to queer theory and its thematic centrality in Jeanette Winterson's novels Oranges Are Not the Only fruit (1985). It is a semi autobiographical novel and it narrates the story of an adopted girl, significantly called Jeanette, who grows up a lesbian inside a strict religious community. It elucidates upon the story of Jeanette's quest for subjectivity and homosexuality but rejects the traditional appropriation of the self by the masculine. It is most obvious example of her realist impulse and her first conscious attempt at deconstructing the reality fiction and echo those of early feminism, in terms of the relationship between mother and daughter. Winterson's concerns with the mother/daughter bond and its dissoluble passionate oppressiveness addresses an issue that is central to feminism as well as to queer. It is a significant example of Lesbian fiction. The novel can be read as Jeanette's journey in trying to find herself and understand her own sexuality, the novel perpetrates a ferociously satirical criticism of religious fundamentalist discourse and their cruel methods of manipulation and the treatment meted out to Jeanette. But these very cruel methods to repress her sexuality towards the end of the novel in fact nurture her own perception of the self and she vindicates and celebrates the existence of same-sex desire, and clearly rejects heterosexuality as "the only fruit."

Keywords: Queer theory, Homosexuality, Lesbian, Feminism, Heterosexuality.

Jeanette Winterson is one of Britain's renowned alternative literary figures and an inventive postmodern author. She was born on 27th August, 1959 in Manchester, England. Her fiction explores the nature and varieties of erotic love within the dynamics of queer theory. This thesis attempts to examine aspects related to queer theory and its thematic centrality in Jeanette Winterson's *oranges are not the only fruit*. She blends many genres into her writings and these include fable, fantasy, history, philosophy, lesbian writing, science fiction, magic realism and scientific studies. The novel has been widely understood as semi-autobiographical as it narrates the story of an adopted girl, significantly called Jeanette, who grows up a lesbian inside a strict religious community. The novel is both the most obvious example of her realist impulse and her first conscious attempt at deconstructing reality. Queer theory ultimately displaces patriarchal gender hierarchy in favor of heterosexuality as the primary regulatory system. *Oranges Are Not the Only Fruit* is both the most obvious example of her realist impulse and her first conscious attempt at deconstructing the opposition reality/fiction.

Winterson's concern with the mother/daughter bond and its indissoluble passionate oppressiveness addresses an issue that is central to feminism as well as to queer. *Oranges Are Not the Only Fruit* is thus a significant example of lesbian fiction. Jeanette's mother believes in literal translations of the Bible, and she freely uses religious rhetoric to accommodate her black and white fashion of viewing the world. Although Jeanette happens to feel greatly connected to her church and her church's teachings, this fidelity towards the supposed perfection of the church becomes challenged as she realizes that she is sexually and romantically drawn towards women. *Oranges are not the only fruit* focuses most of its attention on the tensions and frictions that spark when

Be Eco-Friendly

ISBN-978-93-91115-01-2

Jeanette's sexual life clashes with her religious life, and on the drastic measures that her church takes to drive the "demon" of "unnatural passions" away from her.

Although Jeanette's development and moral growth is most certainly the focus of this novel, a lot of the content is focused on her strange relationship with her mother, and even more so, on the mother's blind and ritualistic devotion to her church. The mother desperately tries to shield Jeanette from evils, especially those associated with gender and sexuality. For instance, when Jeanette develops a friendship with an ostensibly lesbian couple that runs a paper shop, the mother soon forbids Jeanette from going to that store because there was a rumor that "they dealt in unnatural passions" (7). Seeing as the mother doesn't speak to her daughter about matters of gender, sexuality, and the body, Jeanette naively believes that "unnatural passions" are referring to the fact that the couple puts chemicals in their sweets.

This desire to protect Jeanette from evil, in addition to the mother's penchant for explaining phenomena using religious rhetoric, makes it increasingly difficult for Jeanette to adjust to the outer world. For instance, Jeanette goes deaf for three months in the novel. Rather than taking Jeanette to the hospital, the mother begins to inform everyone that Jeanette is "in a state of rapture" (23), and she prevents people from speaking to her. It is Miss Jewsbury, a closeted lesbian, who brings Jeanette to the hospital to be treated for her condition. It is in this moment that Jeanette begins her process of development and maturation: it is the moment in which she realizes that her mother doesn't have all of the right answers, and neither does the church. It is during Jeanette's time at the hospital that the motif of oranges becomes heavily introduced into the narrative, for her mother constantly sends her oranges along with some "get better soon" letters when she doesn't have the time to visit Jeanette. Throughout the novel, the only fruit that Jeanette's mother will give to her is the orange, for it is "The only fruit" (29). Little is said as to why oranges are deemed to be the only fruit worthy of consumption. However, the meaning behind the orange is not necessarily based on the fruit itself, but rather, on how the fruit is used. Furthermore, since oranges are the only fruit that are validated from the mother's perspective, all of other fruit go on to lack legitimacy. Much later on in the novel, when Jeanette gets slightly ill, her mother brings her a bowl of oranges, and the following scenario takes place: I took out the largest and tried to peel it. The skin hung stubborn, and soon I lay panting, angry and defeated. What about grapes or bananas? I did finally pull away the other shell, and, cupping both hands round, tore open the fruit. (113)

In this context, it becomes a little clearer that oranges are representing either gender or heterosexuality. By questioning why she can't have other fruit, Jeanette puts into question the limitations that are imposed on her in terms of her choices and preferences. Notice that she has trouble accessing the orange's pulp, which can symbolize the difficulty that Jeanette has towards complying with a simplistic, limited, heteronormative view of the world. It would be much easier for her to eat grapes or bananas; however, we observe that Jeanette's mother is still coercing her to struggle with oranges.

The entire spectrum of fruit, in this interpretive view, would go on to represent the entire spectrum of gender—the mother's efforts to impose oranges as the only good fruit go on to represent efforts to approach a single gender or sexual orientation has valid and legitimate. This leads Jeanette to one of her many philosophical musings, in which she recognizes the fact that her mother is unable to interpret the world without resorting to the use of inartistic thinking. The desire to steer away from convention and normatively is a staple of this novel. Just as Jeanette desires another fruit besides an orange, she also desires to be romantically involved with someone besides a man. Jeanette's penchant for non-normatively is even expressed in her artistic inclinations

and projects. While Jeanette is in school, she truly strives to win a prize in the school's various artistic competitions. While at first she loses these competitions because of her adherence to religious doctrine, she notices that she still continues to lose competitions even when she presents projects that are non-religious in their themes. Jeanette realizes that even though her masterpiece was definitely the best project submitted to the competition, she loses simply because she steers away from convention. Rather than creating a habitual Easter-themed project for the competition, she strives to be different and creative, which essentially makes Jeanette a queer character in many other aspects besides her sexuality.

Jeanette's queerness certainly causes her a lot of pain and heartache, which is perhaps epitomized when she is publicly accused for being a lesbian while in church. The church members deem that Jeanette and her girlfriend, Melanie, have engaged in homosexual activity because they are possessed by demons. This accusation sparks a lot of commotion in the church, and thus, one of the most confusing and convoluted sections of this novel takes place. After the accusation, Jeanette escapes the church and goes to Miss Jewbury's home. When Jeanette returns home after her encounter with Jewbury, the tension of the novel escalates to an unprecedented degree as members of her church congregation perform an intense exorcism on her.

Traditionally, queer theory questions the permanent norms and identities in favor of deconstructing them. In *The Cambridge Companion to Feminist Theory*, Berthold Schoene defines queer as a designation of "new democratic virtues of nonconformity, civil obedience, and political defiance" (285). Furthermore, he states that queer politics does not exist to singularly seek tolerance or equality, but rather seek to generally "challenge mainstream institutions and accounts" generally (286). Thus, queer serves as a less restrictive and specific platform, and a platform for defiance of ruling societal norms and encompassing a broader group of people. Unlike those identity categories labelled lesbian or gay, queer has developed out of the theorizing of often unexamined constraints in traditional identity politics. Consequently, queer has been produced largely outside the registers of recognition, truthfulness and self-identity. Therefore, queer is an identity category that has no interest in consolidating or even stabilizing itself. Judith Butler suggests that identity, out of the perspective of queer theory, may in fact be performative. If the body "[...] is a field of interpretative possibilities" and "if gender is a kind of doing, an incessant activity performed" (Butler 1), the notion of a fixed approach to identity is inevitably questioned. Furthermore, according to Butler, "performativity is not a singular act, but a repetition and a ritual, which achieves its effects through the naturalization in the context of a body, understood, in part, as a culturally sustained temporal duration" (2).

From this moment, Butler argues, the child is 'girded' (or 'boyed')" (131). Thus, the child's sex or gender is not inherent in its body: rather it is brought about by this initial speech act at the birth. The view that gender is performative seeks to show that what has traditionally been thought of as an internal essence of gender is actually manufactured through a sustained set of acts, posited through the gendered stylization of the body. As Lawler puts it: "Sex and gender are just not internalized (taken on as an identity) but materialized (produced within the material body) (128). Furthermore, both femininity and masculinity are, according to Butler, repeatedly, continually, and performatively constituted.

Consequently, identity is something that is done and achieved rather than innate. As a result, we become what we continually, repeatedly and compulsorily perform. In order to emphasize this view on gender as performative, Butler refers to the French writer, modern feminist and philosopher Simone de Beauvoir who suggests in *The Second Sex* that "one is not born a woman, but, rather becomes one" (Butler 11). In other words, for Beauvoir as well as for

Butler, gender is not fixed, but rather something determined by culture and its laws. In addition, Butler argues that what makes queer so efficient is the way in which it understands the effects of its interventions are not predictable and binary and therefore cannot be anticipated in advance. As for the notions of 'identity' and 'gender', they have traditionally been attached to one another. There has been an ongoing attempt in Western society and culture to establish fixed attitudes in individuals based on gender. Thus, individuals have historically adopted certain expected behaviors according to their sex and gender.

Consequently, from the time we are born, we are immediately categorized as male or female. However, as Alvaro Valladar states in *The Construction of the Homosexual identity in Oranges Are Not the Only Fruit*, "this clearly biological assumption may be challenged or disrupted in many occasions as we grow older when 'gender identity' and 'gender roles' come to play their crucial part" (15). Gender is generally viewed as a set of cultural practices associated to biological sex. As for gender identity, it alludes to the identity an individual develops throughout life, which traditionally coincides with the official features of sex.

Concerning of gender identity, Valladar extends it as "something far more than biological sex, it is the output of a set of cultural values we take in, it is actually the result of our behavior, attitude and performance in life" (16). Thus, he agrees with Butler in that gender identity is performative and culturally constructed. In addition, as for the construction of gender identity, Butler argues that certain political practices enforce traditional gender identities and questions to what extent identity is a normative ideal rather than a descriptive feature of experience (23). Furthermore, Butler states that the regulatory structures governing gender also govern culturally intelligible notions of identity. Hence, the "[...] "coherence" and "continuity" of "the person" are not logical or analytic features of personhood, but, rather, socially instituted and maintained norms of intelligibility" (23). Butler also argues that gender and sexual identities not following the norms risk being excluded:

The cultural matrix through which gender identity has become intelligible requires that certain kinds of "identities" cannot "exist" – that is, those in which gender does not follow from sex and those in which the practices of desire do not "follow" from either sex or gender. "Follow" in this context is a political relation of entailment instituted by the cultural laws that establish and regulate the shape and meaning of sexuality. Indeed, precisely because certain kinds of "gender identities" fail to conform to those norms of cultural intelligibility, they appear only as developmental failures or logical impossibilities from within that domain (24). These passages suggest that gender identity is fluid and complex but, simultaneously, strictly regulated by cultural norms and expectations. As it will be shown, this becomes evident in the novel *Oranges Are Not the Only Fruit* as the protagonist, Jeanette, admits to being a lesbian. As mentioned earlier, queer theory encompasses a broader group of people and serves as a platform for defiance of societal norms. In the case of *Oranges*, these societal norms are epitomized by the rules and rock-solid beliefs set

As mentioned earlier, queer theory encompasses a broader group of people and serves as a platform for defiance of societal norms. In the case of *Oranges*, these societal norms are epitomized by the rules and rock-solid beliefs set by Jeannette's mother, the members of their community, and the pastor governing the religious community which Jeannette and her mother are a part of. These societal norms are eventually rejected by Jeanette, which results in her being an outcast in the society. This experience of exclusion when stepping outside the societal norms and expectations is not new to her, however. As a matter of fact, Jeanette's feeling of being an outsider begins earlier on in the novel: In *Oranges*, what Judith Butler calls "A field

of ethical enmeshment with others and a sense of disorientation for the first-person” (25) is present. This sense of “disorientation” of the first-person narrator is inscribed in the very first words of the first line of the novel: “*Like most people* I lived a long time with my mother and father” (Winterson 3). While pointing to the majority of the people forming the community the narrator refers her readers to, the determiner “most”, which implicitly points to the differential units challenging the ideal of a perfect community: Jeannette is exactly one such exception to the norm, and writing the story of this “disorientated” subject will outline a new trajectory for the self, not *within* her community, but *without* it.

Thus, already at this stage in the novel, the narrator rejects the notion of a normative, binary society where everyone behaves and lives their lives according to the dominant, traditional gender and sexual norms of men and women. The performative aspect of queer theory, and the perspective on storytelling and history as subjective and flexible, applies to the purpose of this essay: To show how the protagonist, by using storytelling and narratives as a platform of performance, ultimately constructs an identity of her own. As previously stated, the importance of storytelling in constructing the protagonist’s identity is essential. Stephen Lawler emphasizes this as he states in the chapter “Stories, Memories, Identities” that identities are closely linked to narratives that identities can be understood as being made through narratives. Furthermore, he considers identities “[...] as ‘made up’ through making a *story* out of *life*” (24).

That is, identities are constructed by the stories we are telling ourselves and others throughout life. As it will be shown, the protagonist in *Oranges, Jeanette*, is engaged in such processes as she produces an identity through assembling various experiences and memories from different narratives. The role of storytelling and narratives in the production of identity are thus significant. Furthermore, according to Lawler, narratives “[...] can be seen as a basic to Western culture, as to many – perhaps all - cultures, although of course what counts as a good or reasonable story varies historically and cross-culturally” (25). Lawler states that we could hardly live without telling stories: “We endlessly tell stories about our lives, both to ourselves and to others; and it is through such stories that we make sense of the world, of our relationship to that world and of the relationship between ourselves and other selves” (Lawler 25). Consequently, the very constitution of identity is constructed over time and through narrative, that is, identity is profoundly social and is continually interpreted and reinterpreted. As Lawler puts it: “So identity is not something foundational and essential, but something produced through the narratives people use to explain and understand their lives” (30).

The identification with others through storytelling is another process affecting the construction of identity. When people put themselves into someone else’s story and rework the story, this reworking process results in a story of their own. Here, there is a difference between factual and fictional narratives. Although there is no moral obligation on fictional narratives to have any relationships to real events in order to affect the construction of identity, factual narratives, on the other hand, are expected to do so. In addition, their narrators often demand that we read them that way. By dedicating herself to fictional stories only, the protagonist Jeanette is not obliged to consider any real events or narrators when constructing her identity, which allows her to dream and narrate freely in her identity constructing process. Concerning storytelling and truth, Judith Butler maintains that “The story of origins is...a strategic tactic within a narrative that, by telling a single, authoritative account about an irrecoverable past makes the constitution of the law appear as a historical inevitability” (46). Similarly, Campulova comments on the notion of the truth of origins as something performative rather than static: “By refuting the myth of origin, and thus, problematizing categories, performativity theory attracts the

attention to performative nature of subjects/hierarchies” (76) This perspective on fluid and changeable identity, regardless of previous history, is applicable to the notion that storytelling is an aspect of performance, which is something that is of great importance in the protagonist’s construction of her identity in *Oranges Are Not the Only Fruit*. As Susan Onega puts it: “Like a fairytale heroine, the only weapon Jeanette has to console herself is the power of her imagination” (20).

The resolution and “conclusion” of the novel focus on Jeanette becoming closely involved with the church as she also begins a relationship with a new church member named Katy. Contrary to the beliefs of her congregation, Jeanette firmly believes that her spiritual and sexual lives are able to coexist. She is soon caught in a compromising situation with Katy, and her mother proceeds to kick her out of their home. This so called failure pushes Jeanette to move to a city and start a new life while unfortunately being deprived of her family and her history. She eventually returns to her old home to visit her mother, who seems to express a degree of ambivalence towards Jeanette—they do talk, but they never discuss Jeanette’s love life. The conclusion, however, shows a surprising revelation: Jeanette’s mother starts its first mission with black people and she serves them pineapple because “she thought that’s what they ate” (172). Because of this, Jeanette’s mother ends up eating many dishes with pineapple in it, while claiming, philosophically, that “oranges are not the only fruit” (172). Thus, while the novel certainly ends in a sad note, indicating that many people still believe that Jeanette is possessed, the mother’s acceptance of other fruit leads the reader to believe that perhaps the mother is not viewing the world in the conceptually simplistic fashion that she used to. Just like white and black communities are starting to coexist in the mother’s church, the mother’s black and white conceptual distinctions start to blur.

References

1. Butler, Judith. *Gender Trouble. Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*. Routledge, 2007.
2. De Beauvoir Simone. *The Second Sex*. Translated by Borde, Constance and Malovany-Chevallier, Sheila. Vintage, 2011
3. Schoene, Berthold. *The Cambridge Companion to Feminist Literary Theory*. Brown University, 2008.
4. Lawler, Stephen. *Identity. Sociological Perspectives*. 2nd ed. Polity Press 2014.
5. Valladar, Alvaro Heras. *The Subversive Politics of Intertextuality: The Construction of the Homosexual Identity in Jeanette Winterson’s Oranges Are Not the Only Fruit*. Dissertation, Universidad de La Rioja, 2014.